
Learning-Centered Leadership of School Heads and Its Moderating Effect on Organizational Culture and Organizational Performance

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ABSTRACT: The study determined the moderating effect of learning-centered leadership of school heads on the relationship between organizational culture and organizational performance. This paper employed descriptive-correlational research design and moderation analysis. Weighted mean, Pearson r, and path analysis were used to analyze the data. There were three standardized questionnaires utilized to collect data. The respondents of the study were 300 elementary, junior and senior high school teachers which were chosen using stratified sampling. Results revealed that the level of organizational culture was high, and the levels of organizational performance and learning-centered leadership of school heads were very high. There was a significant relationship between organizational culture and organizational performance, and learning-centered leadership of school heads and organizational performance. Furthermore, the result of moderation analysis using path analysis revealed the moderating effect of learning-centered leadership of school heads on the relationship between organizational culture and organizational performance was significant. Therefore, the learning-centered leadership of school heads strengthens the relationship between the organizational culture and the organizational performance of teachers. This implies that a positive and thriving culture aligns employees with the organization's objectives, fostering innovation, productivity, and engagement. It enhances satisfaction, provides consistency in decision-making, and attracts and retains teachers, all contributing to enhanced performance.

KEYWORDS: educational management, teachers, organizational culture, organizational performance, learning-centered Leadership, moderation, Philippines

1. INTRODUCTION

In the current context, complexity and uncertainty have increased. This affects the organization's performance. A lack of clear communication and objective alignment inside the organization resulted in inefficiencies, duplicated efforts, and reduced overall production. Poor organizational performance among teachers is detrimental to the organization. According to Hristo (2023), poor organizational performance can negatively impact the whole organization. This can lead to a widespread lack of motivation, production, and customer satisfaction. Other employees may become disenchanted and dissatisfied, resulting in increased tardiness and resignation.

Organizational performance is essential to demonstrate effectiveness and justify its presence in society (Satyendra, 2020). An organization's success can be demonstrated through its improved community reputation. Individual performance can set off a chain reaction, propelling a company's performance to new heights. An organization gains from its employees' performance, productivity, and commitment (Elgendry, 2023). Organizational performance is significant to the success and sustainability of an organization. It promotes growth, encourages innovation, strengthens stakeholder relationships, and determines the organization's ability to survive and thrive in a competitive context.

Organizational culture has the potential to boost educational performance. It enables members to collaborate with mutual trust, loyalty, and high dedication, reducing the workload of completing a task while maintaining high efficiency and effectiveness as an educational institution. According to De La Cruz (2019), employees with a strong culture have values that motivate them to work together to reach a common objective with less questioning, and improved performance is possible.

2. METHOD

2.1 Research Respondents

The survey included 300 teachers as responders, 180, 88, and 32 of whom were from elementary, junior high, and senior high school, respectively. One thousand three hundred sixty-three (1,363) teachers from public elementary, junior high, and senior high schools in Island Garden City of Samal, the Philippines, participated in the study. In order to ensure a fair distribution of respondents from the elementary, junior high, and senior high schools in the Samal Division and to minimize biases, the

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researcher employed the stratified sampling technique. Based on specified characteristics, stratified sampling is a technique that divides the entire population into homogeneous subpopulations known as strata (Shi, 2015). The selected number of participants met the conventional requirement of 300-499 participants for path analysis, a reasonable sample size recommended by Tabacknick and Fidell (1996) and Comney and Lee (1992). As a result, the sample size of 300 for this investigation would be adequate for analysis. The 300 teachers can be anyone who teaches in public elementary, junior high, and senior high school teachers in the Island Garden City of Samal. They were apprised of the goal of the study at the time the survey was administered, and they could not lose their jobs or face consequences if they chose not to participate. The exclusion criterion was considered as the study respondents do not include private and substitute teachers. In case of withdrawal from the included respondents, they will not be forced, and they were given the liberty to withdraw without being penalized as their choices and decisions were respected.

2.2 Materials and Instrument

Three sets of questionnaires modified by various study authors were employed to gather data. The content of the adapted and modified standardized questionnaires is valid because they underwent several changes in order to identify the most trustworthy and legitimate questions. Additionally, the authors have already verified and tested it. Expert validators reviewed the questionnaires to make sure that the questions were comprehensible and that participants were at ease and comfortable answering. An organizational culture questionnaire was utilized to acquire data regarding the independent variable. The adapted and modified version from Van Der Post et al. (1997) represents the following indicators: conflict resolution, culture management, customer orientation, disposition toward change, employee participation, goal clarity, performance orientation, and reward orientation. The Cronbach Alpha result of .983 indicates that the items have relatively high consistency. Furthermore, in acquiring data about the dependent variable of the study, the organizational performance survey questionnaire was used. It is adapted and modified from Paliszkiwicz et al. (2015). The indicators are leadership, trust management, knowledge management with Cronbach Alpha result of .992 which implies that the items have relatively high consistency. The learning-centered leadership questionnaire was used to gain information about the moderating variable of the study. It is adapted and modified from Shen et al. (2018), which includes the following indicators: data-informed decision-making; safe and orderly school operation; high, cohesive, and culturally relevant expectations for all students; distributive and empowering leadership; coherent curricular programs; real-time and embedded instructional assessment; commitment and passion for school renewal with Cronbach Alpha result of .993 which implies that the items have relatively high consistency.

The responses on organizational culture, organizational performance, and learning-centered leadership were analyzed using the scale based on the range of means with its descriptive level and interpretation. The very high descriptive level, with a mean of 4.20-5.00, measures organizational culture, organizational performance, and learning-centered leadership, which are always manifested or always evident. High descriptive level with a range of mean 3.40 – 4.19, which means measures of organizational culture, organizational performance, and learning-centered leadership are often manifested/evident. Moderate descriptive level with a range of mean of 2.60-3.39, which means measures of organizational culture, organizational performance, and learning-centered leadership are sometimes manifested/evident. The low descriptive level with a range of mean 1.80 – 2.59, which means measures of organizational culture, organizational performance, and learning-centered leadership are seldom manifested/evident. Very low descriptive level with a range of mean 1.00 – 1.79, which means measures on organizational culture, organizational performance, and learning-centered leadership are almost never manifested/evident.

The Likert scale was employed to define the degree of learning-centered leadership of school heads and to examine its moderating effect on organizational culture and organizational performance. The items' high reliability was indicated by Cronbach Alpha's total mean score of .989 for the three variables. A total mean score of 4.21 was obtained during the validation process, which was interpreted as very good. It consistently delivers accurate results, is reliable, and can be trusted. A total mean score of 4.21 was obtained during the validation process, which was interpreted as very good.

2.3 Design and Procedure

This study implemented the descriptive-correlational research design to describe the actual existence of the variables, calculate the frequency with which they occur, and classify the data and findings in the exploratory studies as the baseline for prospective hypotheses that may be used to guide further correlational research (Sousa, Driessnack & Mendes 2007). This design benefits education by facilitating and assessing policy, practice, and curriculum design concerns. It assists the administrator in the identification and implementation of practical solutions. In connection, the descriptive correlational technique was suitable for this investigation because its objective was to establish a pertinent correlation between two or more variables. It aims to correlate the variables and determine their significant relationships. Moreover, it also ascertains the learning-centered leadership of school heads and its moderating effect on the relationship between organizational culture and performance.

Additionally, this study implemented moderating effect analysis, in which the learning-centered leadership of the school head serves as the moderator. This is due to the fact that the learning-centered leadership of the school head interacts with the

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relationship between organizational culture and organizational performance. The strength of a relationship between organizational culture and organizational performance may be dependent upon the value of a moderating variable, which is due to the learning-centered leadership of the school heads. The degree of the effect between organizational culture and organizational performance may vary depending on the learning-centered leadership of the school heads as the controlling variable (MacKinnon, 2011).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Organizational Culture

The mean ratings for the organizational culture indicators are displayed in Table 1. With a standard deviation of 0.64, the overall mean of organizational culture is 4.19, which is considered high. This indicates that the teachers' organizational culture is often manifested or evident. The respondents' equally high ratings may have contributed to the high level. The result of calculating the mean scores of the indicators was the mentioned overall mean score. The data suggests that the indicator with the highest mean rating of 4.34, or very high, is goal clarity. On the other hand, indicators that have the lowest average scores of 4.04 or high are performance orientation and reward orientation.

Table 1: Level of Organizational Culture

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Conflict Resolution	0.71	4.08	High
Culture Management	0.72	4.20	Very High
Customer Orientation	0.77	4.31	Very High
Disposition toward Change	0.73	4.31	Very High
Employee Satisfaction	0.70	4.20	Very High
Goal Clarity	0.76	4.34	Very High
Performance Orientation	0.70	4.04	High
Reward Orientation	0.75	4.04	High
Overall	0.64	4.19	High

The implementation of various types of organizational culture in schools substantially influences school success, as evidenced by the results obtained in the level of organizational culture corresponding to the study Lubis (2020). The function of culture in schools is to impart cultural values to school members, cultivate a culture that has been implemented, and transmit the culture to students and instructors. The framework for attaining the quality of education in schools is reflected in the organizational culture. The primary objective of all school personnel is to produce graduates with a high level of quality and a noble character, which is based on their value and conviction in the quality of education.

In addition, the study conducted by Park (2023) supported the notion that the success of all students, personnel, and families is dependent upon the establishment and preservation of a positive school culture. A positive school culture characterizes a sense of safety, respect, and appreciation for all individuals. It is a place where every teacher is enthusiastic about teaching and the students are willing to learn.

3.2 Organizational Performance

Table 2 presents the data on organizational performance. With a standard deviation of 0.72 and a total mean of 4.41, which is very high, the computations show that organizational performance is always manifested. The data show that leadership is the indicator with the highest mean rating of 4.46 or very high. By comparison, knowledge management has the lowest mean rating of 4.37, or very high.

It implies that teachers exhibit a supportive attitude toward their students and have developed instructional strategies that promote optimal organizational performance. Furthermore, schools that exhibit effective management and organization clearly emphasize learning and teaching. Students receive comprehensive support in their diverse curricular and co-curricular pursuits, enabling them to optimize their potential growth and achievement.

Table 2: Level of Organizational Performance

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Leadership	0.76	4.46	Very High
Trust Management	0.77	4.40	Very High

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Knowledge Management	0.73	4.37	Very High
Organizational Performance	0.73	4.40	Very High
Overall	0.72	4.41	Very High

Additionally, this indicates that the capability of the knowledge management process has a very high impact on organizational performance. It is supported by the study of Al Rashdi et al. (2022) which stated that the prioritization of internal knowledge asset management within organizations can substantially impact various aspects of the organization, including its activities, employee development, financial well-being, and internal business processes. This, in turn, contributes to the attainment of superior performance. Furthermore, the results aligned with the research conducted by De La Cruz (2019), which indicated that educators perceived a favorable level of performance within their organization.

3.3 Learning-Centered Leadership of School Heads

The data pertaining to the level of learning-centered leadership of school head is shown in Table 3. The results of the computations showed a very high total mean of 4.39 with a standard deviation of 0.71, indicating that the learning-centered leadership of school heads was always manifested. The data indicates that the real-time and embedded instructional assessment is the indicator with the highest mean rating, 4.44, or very high. On the other hand, the indicator with the lowest mean rating of 4.31, or very high, is data-informed decision-making.

Table 3: Level of Learning-Centered Leadership of School Heads

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Data-Informed Decision-Making	0.99	4.31	Very High
Safe and Orderly School Operation	0.75	4.33	Very High
High, Cohesive, and Culturally Relevant Expectations for all Students	0.76	4.39	Very High
Distributive and Empowering Leadership	0.75	4.39	Very High
Coherent Curricular Programs	0.74	4.36	Very High
Real-Time and Embedded Instructional Assessment	0.73	4.44	Very High
Commitment, and Passion for School Renewal	0.76	4.38	Very High
Overall	0.71	4.39	Very High

It implies that teachers regularly administer exams every two weeks or more frequently across all subject areas and grade levels, and they regularly use formative assessment results to guide future instruction. Every member of the staff, including teachers, is always looking for methods to improve the school's teaching and learning procedures. Teachers also use techniques to completely involve parents as educational partners.

Notably, the result is in line with the study of Aslan et al., 2023, which revealed the relevance of school heads as learning-centered leaders for both students and teachers in their continuing education. Likewise, Al-Mahdy et al. (2021) supported the result by stating that prospective objectives such as student learning and school improvement can be realized through professional development for teachers. Furthermore, it is critical to establish a learning vision and give learning assistance. As a result, leaders must convey a vision that will inspire teachers to learn, provide the necessary resources for learning, and encourage learning-centered activities. It is also critical to organize and manage learning practices and encourage and model professional development through their own experiences. School-based learning approaches allow schools and teachers to tailor learning activities to their specific needs supported by Bellibaş & Gümüş (2021).

3.4 Significance on the Relationship between Organizational Culture and Organizational Performance

Depicted in Table 4.1 is the result of the test of the relationship between organizational culture and organizational performance. Reflected in the hypothesis, the relationship was tested at a 0.05 level of significance. The overall r-value of .863 with a p-value of less than 0.05 signified the rejection of the null hypothesis. This means that a significant relationship exists between organizational culture and performance. This shows that organizational culture is correlated with organizational performance.

Table 4.1: Significance of the Relationship between Organizational Culture and Organizational Performance

Organizational Culture	Organizational Performance				Overall
	Leadership	Trust Management	Knowledge Management	Organizational Performance	
Conflict Resolution	.642**	.620**	.652**	.619**	.658**

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	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Culture	.752**	.731**	.745**	.750**	.773**
Management	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Customer	.809**	.786**	.806**	.810**	.834**
Orientation	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Disposition Toward	.818**	.773**	.814**	.792**	.830**
Change	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Employee	.654**	.665**	.648**	.683**	.688**
Satisfaction	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Goal Clarity	.808**	.786**	.831**	.833**	.846**
Performance	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Orientation	.738**	.709**	.757**	.755**	.768**
Reward Orientation	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	.629**	.618**	.680**	.652**	.669**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Overall	.832**	.809**	.844**	.838**	.863**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

This implies that a positive and thriving culture aligns employees with the organization's objectives, fostering innovation, productivity, and engagement. It enhances satisfaction, provides consistency in decision-making, and attracts and retains teachers, all contributing to enhanced performance. Furthermore, a culture that prioritizes adaptability and ethical behavior facilitates risk management and the facilitation of seamless change management. A well-developed culture is crucial for maintaining high organizational performance and attaining long-term success.

Moreover, this is consistent with the study by Kenedi et al. (2022), which found that organizational culture has a significant positive impact on performance. This demonstrates that all members have understood mainly and internalized the organizational culture. When the organizational culture is adopted and assimilated, these ideals will govern each member's performance. In this environment, the organizational culture, developed and built over time, wields a significant impact in directing members' organizational performance.

According to De La Cruz (2019) which supported the result, employees with a strong culture have values that motivate them to work together to reach a common objective with less questioning, and improved performance is possible. Cultural factors can have a significant impact on school success. Organizational culture has the potential to boost educational performance. It enables members to collaborate with mutual trust, loyalty, and high dedication, reducing the workload of completing a task while maintaining high efficiency and effectiveness as an educational institution.

3.5 Significance on the Relationship between Learning-Centered Leadership of School Heads and Organizational Performance

The findings of the study on the relationship between organizational performance and learning-centered leadership of school heads are shown in Table 4.2. With an overall r-value of .925 and a p-value less than 0.05, the results demonstrate a significant relationship between organizational performance and the learning-centered leadership of school heads, rejecting the null hypothesis. The two variables are correlated as a result.

Table 4.2: Significance of the Relationship between Learning-centered Leadership of School Heads and Organizational Performance

Learning-centered Leadership	Organizational Performance				
	Leadership	Trust Management	Knowledge Management	Organizational Performance	Overall
Data-informed decision-making	.588**	.564**	.591**	.633**	.616**
safe and orderly school operation	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
high, cohesive, and culturally relevant	.839**	.834**	.849**	.878**	.883**
expectations for all students	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
distributive and empowering	.888**	.881**	.887**	.924**	.929**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	.862**	.837**	.812**	.844**	.871**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

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leadership					
coherent curricular programmes	.800**	.793**	.832**	.873**	.856**
real-time and embedded instructional assessment	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
commitment, and passion for school renewal	.874**	.839**	.857**	.869**	.893**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	.862**	.829**	.842**	.854**	.879**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Overall	.892**	.870**	.885**	.918**	.925**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

This implies that the learning-centered leadership of school heads significantly influences organizational performance. This confirms the study of Alanoglu (2023), who concluded that learning-centered leadership significantly impacts teachers' organizational performance. Learning-centered leadership techniques can help teachers improve their organizational performance, create learning school communities and provide all school stakeholders with the support and encouragement they need to learn. By creating a learning vision and demonstrating program management, learning-centered leaders can improve teachers' organizational performance and contribute to a learning school. School heads can increase teachers' sense of justice by selecting weekly class hours fairly, which affects teacher performance.

According to Thien et al. (2022) who supported the result, leaders who prioritize professional development for teachers can help them become masters. Consequently, learning-centered school leaders concentrate on enhancing the members of the organization's learning as well as the learning capacities of teachers and learners alike.

3.6 Moderating Analysis of the Three Variables

Table 5 shows the path analysis of the moderating effect of learning-centered leadership of school heads on the relationship between organizational culture and organizational performance. The result showed a significant relationship between organizational culture and performance, with an estimated value of .590 and a p-value less than 0.05. The relationship between the interaction variable (organizational culture x learning-centered leadership of school heads) and organizational performance is significant, with an estimated value of -.080 and p-value less than 0.05. The relationship between the learning-centered leadership of school heads and organizational performance is significant, with an estimated value of .979 and a p-value <0.05.

Table 5: Moderation Analysis of the Three Variables

Regression Weights: (Group number 1 - Default model)

		Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
Organizational Performance	<--- Organizational Culture	.590	.083	7.084	***	
Organizational Performance	<--- Interaction	-.080	.017	-4.854	***	

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	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
Organizational Performance <--- Learning Centered Leadership	.979	.064	15.262	***	

Regression Weights: (Group number 1 - Default model)

Since all are significant, therefore, **there is a MODERATION EFFECT**

Independent Variable	Moderation Variable	Interaction Variable	Moderation Effect
Significant	Significant	Significant	Yes
Significant	Significant	Not Significant	No
Significant	Not Significant	Not Significant	No
Not Significant	Significant	Significant	Yes

This study's results supported Kanya et al.'s (2021) findings that modifications to organizational culture, teacher efficacy, and school head leadership are necessary to improve performance. Specifically, it is important to note that an organizational culture supported by learner-centered leaders has the potential to enhance teachers' professional development and performance, thereby facilitating collaboration among the entire school community.

4. CONCLUSION

This section presents conclusions based on the study's findings. Respondent public school teachers demonstrated a high organizational culture, very high organizational performance, and very high learning-centered leadership. There is a significant relationship between organizational culture and organizational performance, learning-centered leadership of school heads and organizational culture, and learning-centered leadership of school heads and organizational performance. The study's findings further confirm that learning-centered leadership of school heads has a moderating effect on the relationship between organizational culture and organizational performance.

The results validated the anchored theory based on Elger's Theory of Performance (ToP), cited by Caine (2005). ToP develops and links six basic concepts to create a structure that can be utilized to explain performance as well as performance enhancements. It is advised to perform in order to produce valuable outcomes. One's current performance level is influenced by context, knowledge, skills, identity, fixed elements, and personal characteristics. Three principles are recommended for effective performance enhancement. These include a performer's thinking, immersion in a stimulating environment, and participation in reflective practice.

It is recommended to establish a high organizational culture at work and to put an emphasis on diversity, collaboration, employee recognition, and clear communication. Delve into encouraging constructive feedback and a sense of purpose and belonging. Investing in professional development can ultimately motivate employees and improve their level of fulfillment in their work. Furthermore, setting objectives that are measurable and in line with the Department of Education's mission and vision is also important in achieving exceptionally high organizational performance. Participate in data-driven decision-making and promote a culture of accountability. Encourage employees to be flexible and constantly learning in order to react to opportunities and problems effectively.

Additionally, it is advised that school heads concentrate on modeling lifelong learning, encouraging a growth mindset, and involving teachers in collaborative decision-making in order to develop very high levels of learning-centered leadership. In order to improve student performance, place a strong emphasis on instructional leadership using data-driven tactics and classroom observations. Create professional learning communities for educators so they can collaborate on best practices, encourage creative teaching strategies, and put staff and student welfare first. Establish clear expectations for learning and recognize accomplishments to boost spirits and, in the end, create a vibrant environment that encourages ongoing development.

Overall, it is recommended that schools prioritize the cultivation of a cooperative culture, supportive leadership, and ongoing professional development to enhance teacher performance. It may also recognize the efforts of teachers, promote work-life balance, and provide sufficient resources. Performance may further be improved by establishing clear and achievable objectives, fostering a positive school culture, and promoting the use of student feedback. Schools may guarantee the continued provision of high-quality instruction and improved student outcomes by fostering an environment that prioritizes and encourages teachers.

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